

ID 1176

Analysis of Flexural Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Beam Strengthened with Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Plastic(CFRP)

S.C. Ng and S.Lee
*Advanced Engineering Materials Facility,
Hong Kong University of Science & Technology,
Clear Water Bay, N.T.,
Hong Kong*

Key words: carbon fibre reinforced plastic, strengthening, analysis, reinforced concrete

Abstract:

This paper presents an analytical study on the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with externally bonded carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates. Different failure modes of these strengthened reinforced beams have been reported and these failure modes are generally referred to as brittle failure or ductile failure involving the compression crushing of the concrete, debonding or rupture of the composite laminate and yielding of the steel reinforcement. The analytical solution is derived from the equilibrium equations and the compatibility of the strains, and it is applicable to both singly and doubly reinforced concrete beams strengthened with multi-layers of CFRP laminates. In this study, a simple and direct analytical procedure has been developed to evaluate the flexural capacity of concrete beams strengthened with CFRP and to predict their failure modes. An example is presented to illustrate the computational procedures. For design purposes, the upper and lower limits of CFRP cross-section areas are established to ensure that reinforced concrete beam strengthened with advanced composite materials will fail in a ductile manner. A comparison between the analytical results and the data obtained from the literature has been made and the agreement is very good.

1. Introduction

The development of advanced composite materials for the aerospace industry presents new possibilities for the application of these materials in civil engineering. Advanced composite materials offer advantages such as low weight, excellent handleability, a range of elastic moduli, high resistance to corrosion, high strength, availability in long lengths thus avoiding the need for lapping, and good fatigue and creep characteristics. Recent studies have shown that advanced composite materials can strengthen structural elements such as columns and beams, leading to great economic benefit in repairing damaged deficient structures [1,2,3]. However, the choice of the composite and the manufacturing and application procedures must be well defined to assure that the retrofitted structural elements will consistently have the required performance. In order to characterize these materials and to generate a database for the design procedure for this relatively new repair technology, an extensive experimental program will be conducted to generate design allowable data. Theoretical analysis is a very useful and powerful tool to provide necessary guidance in the design. This study is aimed at developing analytical capabilities for predicting flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with advanced composite materials.

2. Analysis of the cross-section of a beam

Three principles used for the analysis of the cross-section of a beam are:

- (1) Stresses and strains are related by the material properties of concrete, steel and CFRP.
- (2) Strain distribution must be compatible with the distorted shape of the cross-section.
- (3) Resultant forces on the cross-section must be balanced with the applied loads for static equilibrium.

These principles are valid irrespective of how the stresses and strains are distributed, how the member is loaded, and how the shape of the cross-section is elastically changed.

2.1. Stress-Strain Relations

Typical mechanical properties of concrete and steel used in this study are obtained from BS 8110:

The ultimate strength of concrete is given by the following expression:

$$\frac{0.67 f_{cu}}{g_c} = \begin{cases} 0.45 f_{cu} & \text{for } g_c = 1.5 \text{ (design)} \\ 0.67 f_{cu} & \text{for } g_c = 1.0 \text{ (testing)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where a factor of 0.67 is normally used for compensating for the difference between the flexural strength and the cube crushing strength of the concrete, and $g=1.5$ is a safety factor for the strength of the concrete when the designed member is cast *in situ*, or $g=1.0$ when the member is cast in the laboratory for testing. The ultimate strain of $\epsilon_{cu}=0.0035$ is a typical value for all grades of concrete.

The relationship between the stress and strain of steel is presented in the following expression:

$$f_s = \begin{cases} E_s \epsilon_s & \text{if } 0 < \epsilon_s \leq \epsilon_y \\ f_y / g_s & \epsilon_s > \epsilon_y \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

and the yield strain is

$$\epsilon_y = \frac{f_y / g_s}{E_s} \quad (3)$$

At the ultimate strength, the design ($g=1.15$) yield strain is $\epsilon_y=0.2\%$ for high yield steel $f_y=460 \text{ N/mm}^2$, and it is 0.1087% (ϵ_y) for mild steel $f_y=250 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The testing ($\gamma_s=1.0$) yield strain is $\epsilon_y=0.23\%$ for high yield steel and $\epsilon_y=0.125\%$ for mild steel.

The relationship between the stress and strain of CFRP is linear and the elastic range is given in the following expression

$$f_f = E_f \mathbf{e}_f \quad (4)$$

2.2. Distribution of strains and stresses in a cross-section

In analyzing the bending of reinforced concrete beams, it is assumed that the concrete will crack at the ultimate tensile strain. After the concrete fails, all of the tension loads will be carried by the steel reinforcement and the CFRP laminate. It is also assumed that the entire transverse section of a structural member remains in plane after bending and the strain distribution is linear within the section.

Figure 4 shows the cross-section of a rectangular beam subjected to bending and the resultant strain diagram, together with a simplified equivalent rectangular stress block. As there is compatibility of strains between the reinforcement, the adjacent concrete and the CFRP laminate which is bonded to the tension face of the concrete beams, the steel strain \mathbf{e}_s in tension, \mathbf{e}'_s in compression and the CFRP strain \mathbf{e}_f in tension can be determined from the strain diagram. The relationship between the depth of the neutral axis, x , and the ultimate concrete strain, \mathbf{e}_{cu} , and the steel and CFRP strain is given by

$$\mathbf{e}_s = \mathbf{e}_{cu} \frac{d-x}{x} = \mathbf{e}_{cu} \left(\frac{1}{\mathbf{x}} - 1 \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{e}'_s = \mathbf{e}_{cu} \frac{x-d'}{x} = \mathbf{e}_{cu} \left(1 - \frac{\mathbf{d}'}{\mathbf{x}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_f = \mathbf{e}_{cu} \frac{d_f - x}{x} = \mathbf{e}_{cu} \left(\frac{\mathbf{d}_f}{\mathbf{x}} - 1 \right) \quad (7)$$

in which depth factors of the beam section

$$\mathbf{x} = \frac{x}{d}, \quad \mathbf{d}' = \frac{d'}{d}, \quad \mathbf{d}_f = \frac{d_f}{d} \quad (8)$$

where d is the effective depth of the tensile steel reinforcement, d' the depth of the compression reinforcement and d_f is the depth of the CFRP laminates.

Having determined the strains, the stresses in the steel reinforcement and CFRP laminates can be obtained from the stress-strain curves of Figs. 2 and 3, together with the equations developed in section 2.1.

Fig. 4. Cross-section with strain diagram and stress block.

2.3 Equilibrium equation and ultimate moment of resistance

Bending will induce forces acting on the section.

From the equilibrium condition, the equilibrium equation is obtained as:

$$0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{g_c} b x + f'_s A'_s = f_s A_s + f_f A_f \quad (9)$$

That is

$$0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{g_c} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{r}' f'_s = \mathbf{r} f_s + \mathbf{r}_f f_f \quad (10)$$

where the area ratios of tension steel, compression steel and tension CFRP are

$$\mathbf{r} = \frac{A_s}{bd}, \quad \mathbf{r}' = \frac{A'_s}{bd}, \quad \mathbf{r}_f = \frac{A_f}{bd}. \quad (11)$$

The ultimate flexural strength, M (often called the ultimate moment of resistance), of the beam is then obtained by taking moments about a convenient horizontal axis. For example, taking moments about the centroid of the concrete stress block (Fig. 4) gives

$$\frac{M}{bd^2} = \mathbf{r}' f'_s (1 - 0.45 \mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{r}_f f_f (\mathbf{d}_f - 0.45 \mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{r} f_s (\mathbf{d}' - 0.45 \mathbf{x}) \quad (12)$$

or, taking moments about the level of the compression bar yields

$$\frac{M}{bd^2} = 0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{g_c} \mathbf{x} (\mathbf{d}' - 0.45 \mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{r}' f'_s (1 - \mathbf{d}') + \mathbf{r}_f f_f (\mathbf{d}_f - \mathbf{d}') \quad (13)$$

or, taking moments about the level of the tension bar yields

$$\frac{M}{bd^2} = 0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{g_c} \mathbf{x}(1 - 0.45\mathbf{x}) + r'_s f'_s (1 - \mathbf{d}') + r_f f_f (\mathbf{d}_f - 1) \quad (14)$$

or, taking moments about the level of the laminate plate yields

$$\frac{M}{bd^2} = 0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{g_c} \mathbf{x}(\mathbf{d}_f - 0.45\mathbf{x}) - r'_s (\mathbf{d}_f - 1) + r'_y f'_y (\mathbf{d}_f - \mathbf{d}') \quad (15)$$

The M values from these equations are essentially equal in magnitude.

3. Balanced section

3.1. Flexural failure modes

Reinforced concrete beams strengthened with externally bonded CFRP reinforcement could fail in any of the following flexural failure modes (Fig. 5):

- (1) Compression failure, in which the concrete crushes in compression before the reinforcing steel yields;
- (2) Tension failure, in which concrete crushing follows the yielding of the reinforcing steel in tension;
- (3) CFRP rupture, in which the rupture of CFRP laminate follows the yielding of reinforcing steel in tension.

These three failure modes can be schematically illustrated in Fig 5.

Fig. 5. Schematic illustrating failure modes and balanced sections for CFRP strengthened beam.

When the areas of reinforcing bar A_s and CFRP A_f are above certain values (above the line ab in Fig. 5), compression failure of a beam with heavy reinforcement will occur with the crushing of the concrete, while the steel and CFRP strains are still relatively low. This type of failure is characterized by a small deflection of the beam and by the absence of extensive cracking in the tension zone. The failure, often non-ductile and explosive, occurs without early warning.

Tension failure of a beam with light reinforcement is characterized by large steel and CFRP strains, and the beam will exhibit extensive cracking in the concrete and a substantial deflection. This type of failure process is considered to be ductile and it provides ample warning of an impending failure. For practical and economical consideration, designers should aim at designing a beam with a minimal reinforcement while providing the maximum flexural capability, which is the back region in Fig.5.

When the areas of reinforcing bar A_s and CFRP A_f are below certain values (below line cd in Fig. 5), CFRP rupture will occur before the concrete attains the ultimate compressive strain. This type of failure is a less-ductile failure.

From a practical point of view, it is necessary that upper and lower limits of both reinforcing bar and CFRP areas can be established so that a proper amount of reinforcement can be chosen within the range and that the failure of the beam will be in a ductile fashion. For this purpose, analysis of a balanced section for achieving the ductile behavior is presented in the following section:

3.2. Balanced section 1

Section 1 is said to be balanced if the concrete strain ϵ_c reaches the ultimate strain, ϵ_{cu} , simultaneously with the bottom tension steel strain, ϵ_s reaching yield strain, ϵ_y . Meanwhile, the compression steel strain $\epsilon'_s > \epsilon'_y$, and the CFRP strain $\epsilon_f < \epsilon_{fu}$. That is, the strain distribution at collapse is as shown in Fig. 6. The depth factor of the neutral axis $\alpha = x/d$ has a value and is given in eqn (5) with ϵ_s and can be replaced by ϵ_y :

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{\epsilon_{cu}}{\epsilon_{cu} + \epsilon_y} \quad (16)$$

and from eqn (7),

$$\epsilon_f = \epsilon_{cu} \left(\frac{d_f}{\alpha_1} - 1 \right). \quad (17)$$

In this case, the equation of the force equilibrium, given by eqn (10) with f_s replaced by f_y/g and f'_s by f'_y/g , becomes

$$0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{g_c} \alpha_1 + r' \frac{f'_y}{g_s} = r \frac{f_y}{g_s} + r_f f_f \quad (18)$$

A maximum CFRP cross-sectional area $A_{f,max}$ should be provided to prevent a compression failure as follows:

$$\mathbf{r}_{f, \max} = \frac{(0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c)\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{r}'(f'_y/\mathbf{g}_s) - \mathbf{r}(f_y/\mathbf{g}_s)}{E_f \mathbf{e}_f}. \quad (19)$$

Fig. 6. Strain distribution in balanced section 1.

3.3. Balanced section 2

Section 2 is said to be balanced if the concrete strain, e_c , reaches the ultimate strain, e_{cu} , simultaneously with the bottom CFRP strain, e_f , reaching ultimate strain e_{fu} . Meanwhile, compression steel strain $e'_s > e'_y$ and tension steel strain $e_s > e_y$. That is, the strain distribution at collapse is as shown in Fig. 7. The depth factor of neutral axis, $x = x/d$, has a value, which is given in eqn (8) with e_f and can be replaced by e_{fu} :

$$\mathbf{x}_2 = \frac{e_{cu}}{e_{cu} + e_f} \mathbf{d}_f \quad (20)$$

In this case, the equation of the force equilibrium, given by eqn (10) with f_s replaced by f_y/\mathbf{g}_s , f'_s by f'_y/\mathbf{g}_s and f_f by $E_f e_{fu}$, becomes

$$0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{x}_2 + \mathbf{r}' \frac{f'_y}{\mathbf{g}_s} = \mathbf{r} \frac{f_y}{\mathbf{g}_s} + \mathbf{r}_f E_f e_{fu} \quad (21)$$

A minimum CFRP cross-sectional area $A_{f, \min}$ should be provided to avoid a failure, in which the CFRP rupture occurs before the concrete attains the ultimate compressive strain, thus inducing a less-ductile failure, where $k=0.6$ as follows:

$$\mathbf{r}_{f, \min} = \frac{(kf_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c)\mathbf{x}_2 + \mathbf{r}'(f'_y/\mathbf{g}_s) - \mathbf{r}(f_y/\mathbf{g}_s)}{E_f e_{fu}} \quad (22)$$

Fig. 7. Strain distribution in balanced section 2.

4. Computation formulae

In practical cases, the depth factors of the neutral axis, are given by eqns (16) and (20), and \mathbf{x} is within the range of the balanced sections 1 and 2, i.e.,

$$\left(\mathbf{x}_2 = \frac{e_{cu}}{e_{cu} + e_{fu}} \mathbf{d}_f \right) \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \left(\mathbf{x}_1 = \frac{e_{cu}}{e_{cu} + e_y} \right). \quad (23)$$

The equation of the force equilibrium, given by eqn (10) with f_s replaced by f_y/\mathbf{g} , f'_s by f'_y/\mathbf{g} and f_f by $E_f \mathbf{e}_f$, then becomes

$$0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{r}' \frac{f'_y}{\mathbf{g}_s} = \mathbf{r} \frac{f_y}{\mathbf{g}_s} + \mathbf{r}_f E_f \mathbf{e}_{cu} \left(\frac{\mathbf{d}_f}{\mathbf{x}} - 1 \right) \quad (24)$$

Dividing both sides of eqn (24) by $(0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g})$ yields

$$\mathbf{x} + \frac{f_y/\mathbf{g}_s}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r} = \frac{f'_y/\mathbf{g}_s}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r}' + \frac{E_f \mathbf{e}_{cu}}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r}_f \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{d}_f}{\mathbf{x}} - 1 \right) \quad (25)$$

The equation of moment resistance, given by eqn (15) with f_s replaced by f_y/\mathbf{g} and f'_s by f'_y/\mathbf{g} , then becomes

$$\frac{M}{bd^2} = 0.6 \frac{f_{cu}}{\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{x} (\mathbf{d}_f - 0.45\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{r} \frac{f_y}{\mathbf{g}_s} (\mathbf{d}_f - 1) + \mathbf{r}' \frac{f'_y}{\mathbf{g}_s} (\mathbf{d}_f - \mathbf{d}') \quad (26)$$

Dividing both sides of eqn (26) by $(0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g})$ yields

$$\mathbf{x}(d_f - 0.45\mathbf{x}) - \frac{f_y/\mathbf{g}_s}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r} \cdot (d_f - 1) + \frac{f'_y/\mathbf{g}_s}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r}' \cdot (d_f - d') = \frac{M/bd^2}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \quad (27)$$

Introducing the non-dimensional indices of reinforcing steels and strengthening CFRP

$$\mathbf{f} = \frac{f_y/\mathbf{g}_s}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r}, \quad \mathbf{f}' = \frac{f'_y/\mathbf{g}_s}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r}', \quad \mathbf{f}_f = \frac{E_f e_{cu}}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c} \mathbf{r}_f \quad (28)$$

and normalised moment capacity

$$m = \frac{M/bd^2}{0.6f_{cu}/\mathbf{g}_c}, \quad (29)$$

Eqns (25) and (27) become (30) and (31), respectively,

$$\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{f}' = \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{f}_f \left(\frac{d_f}{\mathbf{x}} - 1 \right) \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(d_f - 0.45\mathbf{x}) - (d_f - 1)\mathbf{f} + (d_f - d')\mathbf{f}' = m \quad (31)$$

This pair of equations is the basic set of equations for analysing the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with externally bonded CFRP laminates. Hence, a simple and direct computation procedure for design has been developed for determining the CFRP cross-sectional area, or evaluating the ultimate flexural capacity to ensure ductile behavior of the tension failure of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with CFRP laminate

5. An example for illustration of the procedures

Fig. 8. CFRP-strengthened reinforced concrete beam

6.1. Beam Configuration

A beam section is shown in Fig. 8. The material properties are : $f_{cu}=30 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the concrete, $f_y=250 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the compressive steel, $f_y=460 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the tensile steel and $f_{fu}=4,200 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the CFRP laminates. The modulus of elasticity is $E_s=200 \text{ GPa}$ for the steel and $E_f =235 \text{ GPa}$ for the CFRP laminates. The design/test moment at the ultimate and limit state causes sagging of the beam. The partial safety factors are $\gamma=1.5$ and $\gamma=1.15$ for the design and $\gamma=\gamma=1.0$ for the test.

The section data

The data are as follows:

$$b=150\text{mm}, d=190\text{mm}, d' =30\text{mm}, d_f=220\text{mm},$$

then from eqn (8)

$$\alpha = 0.157, \beta = 1.157$$

and the depth factors of balanced sections from eqns (16) and (20)

$$\alpha_1=0.636 \text{ and } \alpha_2=0.178.$$

Provide two R8 bars for compression reinforcing:

	$A_s = \alpha b d \text{ (mm}^2\text{)}$	100α	β for design	β for test
2-R8	101	0.353	0.0639	0.0490

Provide two T12 or T16 bars for tension reinforcing:

	$A_s = \alpha b d \text{ (mm}^2\text{)}$	100α	β for design	β for test
2-T12	226	0.794	0.2646	0.2028
2-T16	402	1.411	0.4703	0.3606

Provide Reno Carbon Fiber Sheet (MRL-T7-300) of 1-5 ply for strengthening:

	$A_f = \alpha b d \text{ (mm}^2\text{)}$	100α	β for design	β for test
1 ply	25	0.088	0.060	0.040
2 ply	50	0.175	0.120	0.080
3 ply	75	0.263	0.180	0.120
4 ply	100	0.351	0.241	0.160
5 ply	125	0.439	0.301	0.200

6.3. Results and comparison

The computation procedures were presented in Section 5.2. Results and comparison are shown in Table 1.

It is noted that most designs and test failures are from ductile tension because of the fact that

$$(\mathbf{x}_2=0.178) < \mathbf{x} < (\mathbf{x}_1=0.636),$$

except when the compression failure for the design beam using 2-T16 reinforcing and 5-ply CFRP strengthening because of the fact that

$$(\mathbf{x}=0.643) > (\mathbf{x}_1=0.636).$$

Close scrutiny of Table 1 and Fig. 9 reveals several interesting observations:

- (1) The external bonding of the CFRP laminates can significantly increase the ultimate flexural capacity, M , of the reinforced concrete beams.
- (2) This effect is more pronounced for beams having relatively small steel reinforcement area, A_s .
- (3) For any particular reinforced concrete beam, the rate of increase in the ultimate flexural capacity decreases while the CFRP cross-sectional area, A_f , increases.

Table 1 Results and comparison.

Tension bar		2-T12		2-T16	
No. of plies		design	test	design	test
0	ξ	0.2007	0.1538	0.4064	0.3116
	M	0.2369	0.1848	0.3864	0.3095
	M (kN-m)	15.4	18.0	25.1	30.2
1	ξ	0.3424	0.2790	0.4880	0.3898
	M	0.3653	0.3044	0.4474	0.3748
	M (kN-m)	23.7	29.7	29.1	36.5
		54.2%	64.7%	15.8%	21.1%
2	ξ	0.4142	0.3427	0.5415	0.4406
	M	0.4234	0.3598	0.4842	0.4143
	M (kN-m)	27.5	35.1	31.5	40.4
		78.8%	94.7%	25.3%	33.8%
3	ξ	0.4657	0.3890	0.5823	0.4797
	M	0.4622	0.3979	0.510	0.4430
	M (kN-m)	30.0	38.8	33.2	43.2
		95.1%	115.3%	32.1%	43.1%
4	ξ	0.5064	0.4262	0.6154	0.5116
	M	0.4912	0.4269	0.5306	0.4655
	M (kN-m)	31.9	41.6	34.5	45.4
		107.4%	131.0%	37.3%	50.4%
5	ξ	0.5401	0.4574	<u>0.6433</u>	0.5389
	M	0.5142	0.4504	0.5469	0.4839
	M (kN-m)	33.4	43.9	35.5	47.2
		117.0%	143.7%	41.5%	56.3%

6. Section analysis verification

To verify the results of the computation procedure for section analysis, a comparison is made between the ultimate load capacity obtained experimentally by different researchers and the predicted ultimate flexural strength using the analytical method described in this paper. The results of the comparison are summarised in Table 2. All beams were tested with four-point bending over a certain span length. The ultimate load represents the sum of two equally concentrated loads applied to the beam at failure. These results indicate that the analytical method developed in this study is quite accurate in predicting the ultimate flexural capacity of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with externally bonded CFRP laminates. The biggest difference between the ultimate load capacity obtained experimentally and the predicted ultimate flexural strength using the analytical method was around 12%. The difference is quite small when considering all the variations associated with the behavior of reinforced concrete structures.

Table 2 Comparison between experimental and analytical results.

Ref.	Beam no.	B (mm)	d (mm)	A_s (mm ²)	f_y (MPa)	f_{cu} (MPa)	d_f (mm)	A_f (mm ²)	f_{fu} (MPa)	E_f (GPa)
[1]	A	205	400	1520	456	35	455	912	400	37.2
	B			1013						
	2	203	152	253	410	54.8	204	91	2206	138
	3			396						
[17]	4			570						
	5			776						
	6			1013						

Table 2 Comparison between experimental and analytical results (continued).

Reference	Beam no.	d' (mm)	A' (mm ²)	f_{cu} (MPa)	Experimental load (kN)	Calculated load (kN)	difference (%)
[1]	A	55	253	35	320	291.2	8.99
	B				255	253.5	0.60
	2	32	143	54.8	95	105.2	10.50
	3				109	110.3	1.70
[17]	4				108	118.0	9.17
	5				146	128.5	12.12
	6				153	141.6	7.54

7. Conclusions

Theoretical analysis on the flexural behavior of a concrete beam strengthened with carbon fibre reinforced plastic has been carried out. The analysis is based on the assumption that (a) strain distribution is linear at failure, (b) there is a perfect bond between the CFRP laminates and the concrete. Based on this study, several findings are presented as follows:

- A maximal and a minimal value of CFRP section area have been determined and any value within the range for strengthening would enable the beam to fail under tension which is preferable.

- Several non-dimensional parameters have been developed and used for facilitating the analysis and calculations. These parameters are found to be very effective and useful in solving the relatively complex mathematical models.
- As a result of this investigation, a simple and direct computational procedure has been developed for predicting the ultimate flexural capacity of a concrete beam strengthened with carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP).
- A comparison has been made between the analytical results and the experimental results reported in the literature. Generally, the agreement is very good except one result exhibits a discrepancy of 12%.

9: Acknowledgement

The research presented in this paper is funded by the Hong Kong University Grant Council, under a Cooperative Research Centre program (CRC98/01.EG14) and the industrial sponsor is the Lit Cheong Power Engineering Ltd. The authors would like to thank the CRC research team members and the AEMF technical staff for their support

References

- [1] Saadatmanesh, H., and Ehsani, M. R. (1991). "RC beams strengthened with GFRP plates. I: Experimental study." *J. of Struct. Engrg., ASCE*, 117(11), 3417-3433.
- [2] An, W., Saadatmanesh, H., and Ehsani, M. R. (1991). "RC beams strengthened with FRP plates. II: Analysis and parametric study." *Journal of Structural Engineering, ASCE*, 117(11), 3434-3455.
- [3] Meier, U., and Kaiser, H. (1991). "Strengthening structures with CFRP laminates." *Proc., Advanced Compos. Mat. in Civ. Engrg. Struct., ASCE, New York*, 224-232.
- [4] Sharif, A., Al-Sulaimani, G. J., Basunbul, I. A., Baluch, M. H., and Ghaleb, B. N. (1994). "Strengthening of initially loaded reinforced concrete beams using FRP plates." *ACI Struct. J.*, 91(2), 160-168.
- [5] Sierakowski, R. L., Ross, C. A., Tedesco, J. W., and Hughes, M. L. (1994). "Concrete beams with externally bonded carbon fiber reinforced plastic strips." *Proceedings of the Third Materials Engineering Conference: Infrastructure: New materials and Methods for Repair, ASCE, San Diego, California*, 212-220.
- [6] Chajes, M. J., Januszka, T. F., Merz, D. R., Thomson, T. A., and Finch, W. W. (1995). "Shear Strengthening of reinforced concrete beams using externally applied composite fabrics." *ACI Struct. J.*, 92(3), 295-303.
- [7] Quantrill, R. J., Holloway, L. C., and Thorne, A. M. (1996). "Predictions of the maximum plate end stresses of FRP strengthened beams: part II." *Mag. Concrete Res.*, 48(177), 343-351.
- [8] Norris, T., Saadatmanesh, H., and Ehsani, M. R. (1997). "Shear and flexural strengthening of reinforced concrete beams with carbon fiber sheets." *J. of Struct. Engrg., ASCE*, 123(7), 903-911.
- [9] Arduini, M., and Nanni, A. (1997). "parametric study of beams with externally bonded FRP reinforcement." *ACI Struct. J.*, 94(5), 493-501.
- [10] Malek, A. M. (1997). "Analytical study of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with FRP plates or fabrics," PhD dissertation, University of Arizona, Tucson.
- [11] Malek, A. M., Saadatmanesh, H., and Ehsani, M. R. (1998). "Prediction of failure load of R/C beams strengthened with FRP plate due to stress concentration at the plate end." *ACI Struct. J.*, 95(1), 142-152.

- [12] Triantafyllou, T. C. (1998). "Shear Strengthening of reinforced concrete beams using epoxy-bonded FRP composites." *ACI Struct. J.*, 95(2), 107-115.
- [13] Malek, A. M., and Saadatmanesh, H. (1998). "Analytical study of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with web-bonded fiber reinforced plastic plates or fabrics." *ACI Struct. J.*, 95(3), 343-352.
- [14] Malek, A. M., and Saadatmanesh, H. (1998). "On the analysis and design of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with FRP laminates." *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 23(2C), 167-182.
- [15] Saadatmanesh, H., and Malek, A. M. (1998). "Design guidelines for flexural strengthening of RC beams with FRP plates." *J. of Compos. for Constr., ASCE*, 2(4), 158-164.
- [16] Grace, N. F., Soliman, A. K., Sayed, G. A., and Saleh, K. R. (1998). "Behavior and ductility of simple and continuous FRP reinforced beams." *J. of Compos. for Constr., ASCE*, 2(4), 186-194.
- [17] Ross, C. A., Jerome, D. M., Tedesco, J. W., and Hughes, M. L. (1999). "Strengthening of reinforced concrete beams with externally bonded composite laminates." *ACI Struct. J.*, 96(2), 212-220.
- [18] Grace, N. F., Sayed, G. A., Soliman, A. K., and Saleh, K. R. (1999). "Strengthening reinforced concrete beams using fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) laminates." *ACI Struct. J.*, 96(5), 865-874.
- [19] Rabinovich, O., and Frostig, Y. (2000). "Closed-form high-order analysis of RC beams strengthened with FRP strips." *J. of Compos. for Constr., ASCE*, 4(2), 65-74.
- [20] El-Mihilmy, M. T., and Tedesco, J. W. (2000). "Analysis of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with FRP laminates." *J. of Struct. Engrg., ASCE*, 126(6), 684-691.